

TO STUDY DEMOGRAPHIC AND HOUSEHOLDS OF SELF HELP GROUPS URBAN WOMEN

- With reference to Visakhapatnam City

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: In the process of development, the empowerment of urban women is an urgent need since they constitute half of the total population. They should be provided with emancipation from traditional and domestic drudgery. Needful and appropriate attention on their issue will enable them to enjoy a perpetual position in the society is urgent. This paper analyses the perception of the respondents on i.e., Self Help Group (SHG) Women households in Visakhapatnam city.

Methodology: The study is based on both secondary and primary data collected from the Self Help Group, Visakhapatnam. The research study analyzed the perceptions of 800 SHG Women in the Visakhapatnam. Percentage, Mean and ANOVA tests are used to analyse the respondents' data.

Findings: The study shows that before SHG, 50 percent of respondents were housewives, 14.5 percent were private employee, 13.5 percent were house-maids, 9.8 percent were daily wage labor, 7.8 percent were self-employed and the remaining five percent of respondents had occupation.

The study shows that before SHG, a dominated group of respondents are living in Terraced houses (78.3%), 12.3 percent of SHG members are living in Tiled houses and the remaining 9.5 percent of SHG members are living in Thatched house.

It is found from the study that majority of the members (36.8%) save monthly, 31.8 percent of the respondents save bimonthly and the remaining 26.3 percent of the respondents pay fortnightly and the least percent of respondents (5.3%) save weekly.

Originality/value: The paper addressed the empowerment of urban women Households through Self-Help Groups in the Greater Visakhapatnam city in Andhra Pradesh.

Keywords: Self Help Group, Women Empowerment, Need, Objectives, Methodology, Findings and Suggestions.

Paper Type: Empirical Paper

INTRODUCTION

Women empowerment has become a burning issue all over the world including India since last few decades. Many agencies have emphasized in their reports that gender issue is to be given utmost priority. It is held that women now cannot be asked to wait any more for equality. Inequalities between men and women and discrimination against women have also been age-old issues all over the world. There should be no discrimination between men and women. Women should now have their fundamental and social rights which they get once they are born. They have demanded equality with men in matters of education, employment, inheritance, marriage, health, and politics. Thus, women empowerment itself elaborates that social rights, political rights, economic stability, judicial strength and all other rights should be also equal to women also (V.P. Gupta, 2017) .

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To analyze the perception of SHG Women households in Visakhapatnam city.
2. To suggest suitable measures to empower women in India through SHGs

SAMPLING

Since the present study addressed itself to study the empowerment of urban women through Self-Help Groups, all the women SHG members of urban areas of Greater Visakhapatnam city in Andhra Pradesh state are formed the universe of the study. Convenience sampling technique has been adopted for selecting the respondents for this study. The detailed number of SHGs and sample respondents selected for the study has been presented in the following tables. The zonal wise population was taken for the selection of the sample.

The research population was spread in Visakhapatnam as shown below

Research Area	Zones	Wards	No. of SHGs	Total members	Sample
Visakhapatnam	Zone-1	1 – 6 wards	2729	27,247	800
	Zone-2	7 – 18 wards	2293	25,223	
	Zone-3	19 – 30 wards	2916	32,076	
	Zone-4	31 – 49 wards	5717	65,745	
	Zone-5	50 – 65 wards	5578	55,780	
	Zone-6	66 – 72 wards	2522	25,196	
Total		72 wards	21,755	2,31,267	

Source: GVMC records

The sample size is calculated after conducting the pilot study using the results obtained from the pilot study and by using the below formula the sample was obtained as 800.537. So, the researcher has selected the sample size as 800.

$$n = \frac{\left(\frac{P[1-P]}{Z^2 + \frac{P[1-P]}{N}} \right)}{R}$$

Where:

- n = sample size required
- N = number of people in the population
- P = estimated variance in population, as a decimal: (0.5 for 50-50, 0.3 for 70-30)
- A = Precision desired, expresses as a decimal (i.e., 0.3, 0.05, 0.1 for 3%, 5%, 10%)
- Z = Based on confidence level: 1.96 for 95% confidence, 1.6449 for 90% and 2.5758 for 99%
- R = Estimated Response rate, as a decimal

As we know that the total population is N= 2,31,267 based on the pilot study the researcher have estimated the variance in the population as P=50, percent=0.5, and precision desired is assumed to be A=5, percent=0.05, and the confidence interval is assumed at 3.46 percent, then the table value of normal Z=2.78 and the response rate is found to be R=0.99 considering the pilot study.

DATA ANALYSIS

1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Age

S. NO	Demographics	Respondents (Percentage)
1	Age	
	20-25 years	48 (6.0)
	25-30 years	82 (10.3)
	30-35 years	262 (32.8)
	35-40 years	230 (28.8)
	Above 40 years	178 (22.3)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The distribution of sample respondents by their age group is presented in the above table. It shows that a dominated group of respondents are 30-35 years in the age group (32.8%), followed by 28.8 percent are 35-40 years, 22.3 percent are above 40 years, 10.3 percent are 25-

30 years and the remaining 6.0 percent of respondents are 20-25 years in the age group. Hence, it can be concluded that the majority group of SHG members are 30-35 years in the age group.

Education level

	Education level	
2	Illiterate	258 (32.3)
	Primary	154 (19.3)
	Secondary	174 (21.8)
	Intermediate	146 (18.3)
	Graduate & above	68 (8.5)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The above table infers that the distribution of sample respondents by their education level. From the total sample SHG members, the highest group of respondents are illiterates (32.3%), 21.8 percent of respondents have secondary education qualification (21.8%), 19.3 percent of respondents have primary education, 19.3 percent have primary education qualification, 18.3 percent have intermediate qualification and only 8.5 percent of respondents are graduates & above. Hence, it can be inferred that most of the respondents are illiterates.

Community-Wise distribution of Respondents

	Community	
3	Forward Casted	148 (18.5)
	Backward Caste	384 (48.0)
	Most Backward Caste	112 (14.0)
	Scheduled Caste	156 (19.5)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The above table-5.1 infers about the community-wide distribution of sample SHG members, nearly fifty percent of respondents are backward caste (48.0%), 19.5 percent of

respondents are scheduled caste, 18.5 percent are forward caste and a significant number of respondents are most backward caste. It is clear that the majority group of SHG members is backward caste.

Religion-Wise distribution of Respondents

	Religion	
4	Hindu	600 (75.0)
	Muslim	106 (13.3)
	Christian	94 (11.8)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

According to the above table-5.1 discusses the religion-wise distribution of sample respondents, three-fourths of respondents are Hindus (75.0%), 13.3 percent are Muslim and the remaining only 11.8 percent of respondents are Christians. Therefore, the above analysis infers that most of the respondents are Hindus.

Occupation-Wise distribution of Respondents

	Occupation	
5	Housewife	396 (49.5)
	Self-employed	62 (7.8)
	House-maids	108 (13.5)
	Daily wage labor	78 (9.8)
	Private employee	116 (14.5)
	Others	40 (5.0)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The above table-5.1 reveals that the distribution of sample respondents by their occupation levels before and after joining in SHG. It shows about SHG members who are before joining in SHG, nearly fifty percent of respondents are housewives (49.5%), 14.5

percent are a private employee, 13.5 percent are house-maids, 9.8 percent are daily wage labor, 7.8 percent are self-employed and the remaining five percent of respondents have other occupation. Among the SHG members who are after joining in SHG, the highest group of respondents are self-employed (28.8%), 24.3 percent are housewives, 20.3 percent are private employees, 10.5 percent are daily wage labor, 10.0 percent have other occupation and the only six percent are house-maids. Therefore, the above analysis infers that prior to joining the SHG, majority of the population were housewives and now have changed to being self employed after joining the SHG, because SHG provides loans for developing women empowerment.

Marital Status-wise distribution of sample respondents

	Marital Status	
6	Unmarried	42 (5.3)
	Married	582 (72.8)
	Widow	92 (11.5)
	Divorced	84 (10.5)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The distribution of sample SHG members by their marital status is presented in the above table-5.1. It shows that more than seventy percent of respondents are married (72.8%), 11.5 percent are widows, 10.5 percent of respondents are divorced and the remaining 5.2 percent of respondents are unmarried. Hence, it is clear that most of the respondents are married in the study area.

Distribution of sample respondents by type of family

	Type of family	
7	Nuclear family	542 (67.8)
	Joint family	258 (32.3)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The distribution of sample of SHG members by type of family is shown in the above table. Among the total sample respondents, more than two-thirds of respondents live in a nuclear family (67.8%) and the remaining 32.3 percent of respondents live in a joint family. Hence, it is clear that the majority group of respondents live in a nuclear family.

Distribution of sample respondents by their family size

	Family size	
8	Below 3 members	180 (22.5)
	3-5 members	446 (55.8)
	6-7 members	76 (9.5)
	Above 7 members	98 (12.3)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The above table-5.1 reveals the distribution of sample respondents according to their family size. It shows that above half of the percent of respondents family size is 3-5 members (55.8%), followed by below 3 members (22.5%), above 7 members (12.3%) and the remaining 9.5 percent is of 6-7 members. Hence, it can be concluded that most of the respondents' family size is 3-5 members.

Earning members of the family

	Earning members	
9	One	416 (52.0)
	Two	280 (35.0)
	Three	64 (8.0)
	Above three	40 (5.0)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The above table-5.1 discussed earning members in the family, a dominated group of respondents said one member (52.0%), followed by two members (35.0%), above three members (8.0%) and three members (8.0%). The above analysis shows that most of the respondents have one member as the breadwinner of the family.

Duration of membership in SHG

10	Duration of membership in SHG
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	4 years	236 (29.5)
	Above 4 years	564 (70.5)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The above table-5.1 shows the duration of membership in SHG. Around seventy percent of SHG members have above 4 years membership in SHG (70.5%) and the remaining i.e. nearly thirty percent of respondents have 4 years membership in SHG. Hence, it is clear that most of SHG members have above 4 years membership in SHG.

Housing Conditions

The housing conditions of respondents are discussed in the following table in a brief

Type of House

Type of Housing	Pre-SHG Period	Post-SHG Period
Thatched	76 (9.5)	46 (5.8)
Tiled	98 (12.3)	80 (10.0)
Terraced	626 (78.3)	674 (84.2)
Total	800 (100.0)	800 (100.0)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The above table-5.1.2 indicates the pre-SHG period of SHG members, i.e. a dominated group of respondents are living in Terraced houses (78.3%), 12.3 percent of SHG members are living in Tiled houses and the remaining 9.5 percent of SHG members are living in Thatched house. Among the post-SHG period, above eighty percent of SHG members are living in the Terraced house (84.2%), ten percent of respondents are living in Tiled houses and only 5.8 percent of SHG members are living in Thatched houses. Hence, it can be concluded that the majority group of respondents are living in a Terraced house.

Ownership status of the house

Ownership	Pre-SHG Period	Post-SHG Period
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Owned	424 (53.0)	494 (61.8)
Rented	340 (42.5)	278 (34.8)
Leased	36 (4.5)	28 (3.5)
Total	800 (100.0)	800 (100.0)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The table-5.1.3 infers the ownership status of the house. The highest group of SHG members have an own house before SHG period (53.0%), followed by rented houses (42.5%) and leased houses (4.5%). The post-SHG period shows that, 61.8% of SHG members have own houses (61.8%), 34.8 percent have rented houses and only 3.5 percent of respondents have leased houses. It is clear that the majority group of SHG members have own houses.

Number of rooms

Number of rooms	Pre-SHG Period	Post-SHG Period
One	300 (37.5)	164 (20.5)
Two	280 (35.0)	378 (47.3)
Above two	220 (27.5)	258 (32.3)
Total	800 (100.0)	800 (100.0)

*Source: Primary data, Figures in parentheses indicate percentages

The above table-5.1.4 indicates the pre-SHG period of SHG members related to number of rooms in their house. A dominated group (37.5%) of respondents have one room in Pre-SHG Period, 35 percent have two rooms and (27.5%) leased houses of above two rooms. It shows in post-SHG period that above forty percent (47.3%) of SHG have two number of rooms and above thirty two percent (32.3%) of SHG numbers have above two rooms and only 20.5 percent of respondents have leased with one room. Hence, it can be concluded that the majority group of respondents have two rooms in post SHG period when compared to the pre-SHG period.

Basic particulars of the respondents based on Pre and Post SHG period

Particulars	Pre-SHG Period	Post-SHG Period
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	Pre-SHG Period		Post –SHG Period	
	N	Mean	N	Mean
Husband / family members	582	12388.32	582	12993.13
Cattle	416	3659.13	416	4781.73
Poultry	234	10303.42	234	13145.30
Rent	340	7639.41	278	12139.57
Interest & others	76	4039.47	76	5725.79
Self (Respondent)	404	7106.44	800	9983.25
Total household income	800	18625.75	800	21871.95

*Source: Primary data

Income from various sources of Pre-SHG and Post-SHG period were compared in the above table-5.2.1. The mean income of the husband/family members before SHG period is 12388.32 and post-SHG is 12993.13. So, it is evident that the mean incomes of the family members were increased after joining the SHG.

The mean income from the cattle before SHG period is 3659.13 and post-SHG is 478.73. So, it is evident that the mean income of the SHG members from cattle has increased after joining SHG.

The mean income from poultry before SHG period is 10303.42 and post-SHG is 13145.30. So, it is evident that the mean incomes of the SHG members from poultry has increased after joining SHG.

The total average income from various sources before SHG period is 10303.42 and post-SHG is 13145.30. So, it is evident that the mean incomes of the SHG members from the poultry has increased after joining SHG. Therefore, it is clear that the women have become financially strong after joining SHG.

Household Expenditure

Many women members independently involved in the economic activities individually and with other group members after joining SHGs. Therefore, they are now economically independent and contribute to increasing their household income. The family expenditure has been increased due to positive change in the SHGs members’ income. Various kinds of expenditure before SHG and after SHG were shown below.

Household Expenditure

Items	Amount per month
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	Pres-SHG Period		Post –SHG Period	
	N	Mean	N	Mean
Food	800	3584.00	800	4222.75
Clothing	800	263.08	800	312.07
Rent	200	4930.00	192	5081.25
Fuel and Electricity	800	260.75	800	429.58
Education	800	3664.67	800	4048.92
Medical Expenses	800	1149.79	800	1557.79
Social and Religious Ceremony	800	3365.25	800	4743.50
Entertainment	542	579.34	538	797.03
Smoking/Drinking	100	442.00	84	405.95
Repayment of loans	800	955.00	800	1177.50
Miscellaneous	800	188.00	800	399.00
Total	800	15110.78	800	18689.23

*Source: Primary data.

It is evident from the above table-5.2.2 that:

The mean expenditure on food before joining SHG was 3584 and after joining SHG was 4222.15. Therefore, we can say that the expenditure of the women on food has increased after joining SHG.

The mean expenditure on clothing before joining SHG was 263.08 and after SHG was 312.07. Therefore, we can say that the expenditure of the women on clothing has increased after joining SHG.

The mean expenditure on house rent before joining SHG was 4390.008 and after SHG was 5081.25. Therefore, we can say that the expenditure on house rent of the women has increased after joining SHG.

The mean expenditure on fuel and electricity before joining SHG was 260.75 and after joining SHG was 429.58. Therefore, we can say that the expenditure on fuel and Electricity of the women has increased after joining SHG.

The mean expenditure on education before joining SHG was 3664.67 and after joining SHG was 4048.92. Therefore, we can say that the expenditure on education of the women has increased after joining SHG.

The mean medical expenses before joining SHG was 1149.67 and after joining SHG was 1557.79. Therefore, we can say that the medical expenses of the women has increased after joining SHG.

Entertainment is nothing but the action of providing or being provided with amusement or enjoyment. The researcher tried to know the expenditure on entertainment before and after joining SHG. It is evident from the above table that the means of entertainment before joining SHG was 579.34 and after joining SHG, the mean score was 797.03 Therefore, we can say that the expenditure on entertainment of women has increased after joining SHG.

It is also evident that the mean values for smoking, repayments of loans, miscellaneous expenses before joining SHG were greater than the expenditure done after joining SHG. Hence the respondents have increased their expenditure after joining SHG.

Savings & Debits of the Households

The members of the SHG are encouraged to save and internally lend the savings to members during times of need. SHPIs also provide knowledge on managing books of accounts. Individuals are organized in groups known as Self Help Groups (SHGs) by NGOs commonly known as Self Help Promoting Institutions (SHPI). The SHGs are also encouraged to take up livelihood activities, for which skill training is provided by certain NGOs. Various modes of savings by the self-help group is shown below.

Mode of Savings

Mode savings pre-SHG and Post-SHG are shown in the table below

Mode of savings Pre-SHG and Post-SHG

Institutions	Amount per month			
	Pres-SHG Period		Post –SHG Period	
	N	Mean	N	Mean
SHGs	-	-	800	1177.00
Cash in hand	800	1090.13	800	1478.00
Chit fund	152	3118.42	152	3157.89
Post Office	74	622.97	80	946.25
Bank	712	820.22	712	1425.00
Provident Fund	62	1203.23	62	1435.48
Friends and Relatives	136	833.09	136	1206.62
NABARD	92	1186.96	92	1567.39

Others	106	947.17	106	1324.53
Total	800	2970.12	800	5287.00

*Source: Primary data.

From the above table-5.2.3, it is evident that savings from various sources have increased after joining into SHGs. But, the highest mean of saving is done in banks. The mean mode of saving before SHG is 820.22 and post-SHG the average savings through bank mode is 1425. The next best mode of saving is cash in hand. The SHG member's cash in hand increased after joining SHG. The mean for chit-fund mode of saving before SHG was 3118.41 and after joining SHG was 3157.89. This was the lowest mode of saving when compared to all other modes of savings.

Periodicity of saving

Periodicity of Savings of SHG members are shown below:

Periodicity of Savings of SHG members

Response	Frequency	Percent
Weekly	42	5.3
Fortnightly	210	26.3
Monthly	294	36.8
Bi monthly	254	31.8
Total	800	100.0

*Source: Primary data.

The above table-5.2.3(1), discusses the Periodicity of saving money of sample respondents. It is found that majority of the members (36.8%) save monthly, 31.8 percent of respondents save bi monthly and the remaining 26.3 percent of respondents pay fortnightly and least Percent of respondents (5.3%) pay weekly. Hence, it can be inferred that most SHG members pay monthly subscription.

Asset Holdings

Assets of SHG members Pre-SHG and Post-SHG are shown and compared in the following table.

Comparison of Assets value between Pre-SHG and Post-SHG.

Items	Amount per month			
	Pre-SHG's value (in Rs.)		Post-SHG's value (in Rs.)	
	N	Mean	N	Mean
Furniture	420	16423.81	422	17244.08
Utensils	800	7002.50	800	8752.50
Jewels	800	151092.50	800	201480.00
Electronic goods (T.V., Radio, etc).	648	17537.04	726	22253.44
Cycle/Motor Cycle	434	49640.55	562	59964.41
House (s)	78	1507692.31	78	1492307.69
Agriculture land	98	73795.92	98	74265.31
Cattle	412	91673.79	412	97730.00
Poultry	236	103731.19	234	106245.30
Sheep/Goat	96	15070.83	96	20385.42
Bullock Carts	116	42651.72	116	18025.86
Others	174	1252.87	174	1389.66
Total	800	449970.70	800	523016.20

*Source: Primary data

Various kinds of assets were bought by SHG members after joining SHGs which is shown in the above table-5.2.4. They were developed after joining SHG. The properties they got after becoming SHG member are as follows. The mean value of the asset “furniture” before joining SHG was 16,423.81 and after joining SHG the value of furniture of the SHG members was 17,244.08. The mean value of the asset has increased after becoming an SHG member. So, it is evident that the SHG members have developed after joining into SHG.

The mean value of the asset “utensils” before joining SHG was 7002.50 and after joining SHG the value of “utensils” of the SHG members was 8752.50. The mean value of the asset has increased after becoming an SHG member. So, it is evident that the SHG members have developed after joining SHG.

The mean value of the asset “Jewels” before joining SHG was 151092.50 and after joining SHG the value of “jewels” of the SHG members increased to 201480.00. The mean value of the asset has increased after becoming an SHG member. So, it is evident that the SHG members have developed after joining SHG.

The mean value of the asset “electronic goods” before joining SHG was 17537.04 and after joining SHG the value of “jewels” of the SHG members was increased to 22253.44. The mean value of the asset has increased after becoming an SHG member. So it is evident that the SHG members have developed after joining into SHG.

The mean value of the asset “cycle/motorcycle” before joining into SHG was 49640.55 and after joining into SHG the value of “cycle/motorcycle” at the SHG members increased to 59964.41. The mean value of the asset has increased after becoming an SHG member. So, it is evident that the SHG members have developed after joining into SHG.

The mean value of the asset “house” before joining SHG was 1507692.31 and after joining SHG the value of “house” of the SHG members was 1492307.69. The mean value of the asset has increased after becoming an SHG member. So, it is evident that the SHG members have developed after joining into SHG.

The mean value of the asset “Agriculture land” before joining SHG was 73795.92 and after joining SHG the value of “Agriculture land” of the SHG members was 74265.30. The mean value of the asset has increased after becoming an SHG member. So, it is evident that the SHG members have developed after joining SHG.

The mean value of the asset “cattle” before joining SHG was 91673.79 and after joining SHG the value of “cattle” of the SHG members was 97730.00. The mean value of the asset has increased after becoming an SHG member. So, it is evident that the SHG members have developed after joining SHG.

The mean value of the asset “poultry” before joining SHG was 103731.19 and after joining SHG the value of “poultry” at the SHG members was 106245.30. The mean value of the asset has increased after becoming an SHG member. So, it is evident that the SHG members have developed after joining into SHG. It can be noted that after joining SHGs, the members have also earned and increased assets like bullock carts, sheep/goat and others.

Household Indebtedness

The following table shows that the indebtedness of SHG members

Indebtedness of SHG members

Agency	N	Average loan amount	The average rate of interest
Loan from SHG	800	37525.00	0.25
Money lenders	90	56688.89	2.25
Friends and Relatives	128	16531.25	2.75
Traders	142	5042.25	3.15
Bank Loan / LIC	122	60140.98	2.50
Others	114	39342.11	3.00

*Source: Primary data

From the above table-5.2.5, it is evident that the SHG members can avail loan facilities for finance from various sources. But the rate of interest for the borrowings is different. From the above table, it is very clear that the highest average money taken through bank loan / LIC

at an average interest rate is 2.5 percent. Similarly, the next highest average value is money lenders at the rate of 2.25. The average household indebtedness for money lenders is 56668. The next highest average amount taken by the SHG members is a loan from SHGs. Its average is 37, 525 at an interest rate 0.25 percent. Therefore, it is very clear that the SHG members are getting financial assistance from SHG loans at cheaper cost.

Who spends the borrowing loan amount?

Response	Frequency	Percent
Self	214	26.8
Husband	504	63.0
Other family members	82	10.3
Total	800	100.0

*Source: Primary data

The above table reveals the distribution of sample respondents reasons to borrow loan amount. It shows that the majority of respondents husbands (63%) spend the borrowed loan amount, while only 26.8% of the respondents spend the borrowed amount on themselves, and the least number of respondents (10.3%) spend on their other family members. Hence, it can be concluded that majority of the respondents have Husbands spending the borrowed loan amount.

Do you repay the loan regularly?

Response	Frequency	Percent
Yes	582	72.8
No	218	27.3
Total	800	100.0

*Source: Primary data.

The perceptions on loan repayment are shown in the above table. 72.8 percent of the respondents are repaying the loan very regularly and only 27.3 percent of the respondents are not repaying regularly.

If yes, what is the source of prompt repayment?

Response	Frequency	Percent
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Income from Employment	348	43.5
Income from investment of loan amount	124	15.5
*Loan from other sources	110	13.8
Total	582	72.5

*Source: Primary data.

Out of the total sample of urban women, a dominated group of respondents (43.5 percent) felt that they are regularly repaying the loans because of their employment, 15.5 percent felt by their income from the investment of loan amount, 13.8 percent of the respondents are repaying their loan promptly because of their income through investments. Hence, it can be concluded that the majority group of respondents are repaying promptly. Hence, the members who have employment are repaying the loan promptly when compared with the members who are getting Income from investment of loan amount.

For what purpose did you get a loan?

Purpose	N	Mean
Agriculture and allied activities	72	36194.44
Consumption	52	30634.62
Start a business	228	33412.28
Purchase of raw materials	260	36841.54
Run the business	172	51404.07
Repayment of loan	228	10006.40
Education	330	40387.27
Others	442	29850.90

*Source: Primary data.

The above table shows the data regarding the purpose of procuring a loan. The mean for the purpose of running the businesses is 51404.07, whereas the mean for the purpose of ‘education’ is 40,387.27. Similarly, the mean for the purpose of ‘purchase of raw material’ is 36,841.54, and the mean for the purpose ‘to start a business’ is 33,412.24, and the mean for the purpose of ‘consumption’ is 30,634.62.

Hence, from the above table, we can conclude that the highest number of SHG members has used the loan amount to run the business and very few SHG members have used the amount for the repayment of the loan.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- 1. Occupation:** The study shows that before SHG, 50 percent of respondents were housewives, 14.5 percent were private employee, 13.5 percent were house-maids, 9.8 percent were daily wage labor, 7.8 percent were self-employed and the remaining five percent of respondents had occupation.
It can also be observed from the study that, after joining SHG, the highest group of respondents are self-employed (28.8%), 24.3 percent are housewives, 20.3 percent are private employees, 10.5 percent are daily wage labor, 10.0 percent have other occupations and the only six percent are house-maids.
- 2. Distribution of sample respondents by type of family:** It is clear from the analysis that, among the total sample respondents, more than two-thirds of respondents are nuclear family (67.8%) and the remaining 32.3 percent of respondents are joint family. Hence, it is clear that majority group of respondents are from nuclear family.
- 3. Duration of membership in SHG:** From the study it can be observed that, around (70 percent) of SHG members have above 4 years membership in SHG and the remaining (nearly thirty percent of respondents) have 4 years membership in SHG.
- 4. Housing Conditions:** The study shows that before SHG, a dominated group of respondents are living in Terraced houses (78.3%), 12.3 percent of SHG members are living in Tiled houses and the remaining 9.5 percent of SHG members are living in Thatched house.
It can also be observed from the study that, among the post-SHG period, above 80 percent of SHG members are living in the terraced house (84.2%), 10 percent of respondents are living in Tiled houses and only 5.8 percent of SHG members are living in Thatched houses.
- 5.** It is noticed from the analysis that, for the separate bathroom particulars in Pre-SHG, 86 percent responded 'Yes', while remaining 14 per cent said 'No'. However, in Post-SHG period, majority of them (95 per cent) responded 'Yes'. while remaining 5 per cent said 'No'
- 6. Mode of Savings:** About periodicity of saving money by the sample respondents, it is found from the study that majority of the members (36.8%) save monthly, 31.8 percent of the respondents save bimonthly and the remaining 26.3 percent of the respondents pay fortnightly and the least percent of respondents (5.3%) save weekly. Hence, it can be inferred that most SHG members pay monthly subscription.
- 7. Source of prompt repayment:** From the analysis, out of the total sample urban women, a dominated group of respondents felt that they are regular by making repayment of loan by income from employment (43.5%).
- 8. Purpose to get a loan from SHG:** Almost 60 percent of the respondents from the study said that the purpose to get a loan from SHG is to start a business and for purchasing raw materials.

SUGGESTIONS FOR BETTER FUNCTIONING OF SHGS

- 1.** It is evident from the study that, there is only a slight increase in the monthly earnings after joining SHG. This will help to increase their monthly earnings.
- 2.** It is observed from the study that the SHG members developed their living standards after joining SHGs. It shows that SHG members are collectively utilizing the benefits of different government schemes to enhance their living standards. So, the government should continue to extend this support to the SHG's.
- 3.** The group members should save the amount from their income to improve their economic conditions. They should save the amount in proper government authorize banks or institutes for security.
- 4.** SHG group should utilize the loan amount properly for their business development and they should repay the loan in time to gain the confidence of loan provided banks or institutes..
- 5.** SHG group should try to extend the area of their business and reach the local market for their home made products.

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